

**AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF CUTOMER'S
EXPECTATION AND PERCEPTION IN TELECOM
SECTOR OF UDAIPUR CITY**

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ABSTRACT

In today's information age, the telecommunication industry has a vital role to play. First telephony started in 1882 in India. Major players of India in the sector are BSNL , Vodaphone, Airtel, Tata Indicom , Reliance , Idea etc. Telecommunication helps in the growth of business and economy. India phases the dynamic midway. Customer mindset is changing very rapidly and it is very difficult to predict that. Hence there is a need to study the customer expectation and perception in telecom sector. This research will be a great help in the decision making process of telecom industry managers. We are using the SERVQUAL model and the study aimed to examine the impacts of reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy and tangible aspects on customer satisfaction towards telecom services. Gap analysis was used to determine the perceived importance and satisfaction on each dimension of service quality.

The results of this study would help management to identify the strengths and weaknesses of service quality so that they can implement an effective strategy to meet the customers' expectations by filling the gap between expected and perceived.

Keywords: *Telecom Sector-Outlets, Customer, Expectation, Perception etc.*

INTRODUCTION

Telecom services have been acknowledged globally as an essential tool for the socio-economic development of a nation. India is currently the world's second-largest telecommunications market and has registered exceptional growth in the past few years. Although the Indian telecom industry is one of the fastest-growing industries in the world, the current teledensity or telecom penetration is extremely low when compared with global standards.

We are using the servqual model to examine the gap between expectation and perception of customers towards telecom services. The results of the study will help managers in their decision making process. In this modal we are using the five dimensions for analysing the gap between the customer expectation and perception.

The five dimensions are as follows:.

The telecom services have been recognized the world-over as an important tool for socioeconomic

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Development for a nation and hence telecom infrastructure is treated as a crucial factor to realize the socio-economic objectives in India. Accordingly, the Department of Telecom has been formulating developmental policies for the accelerated growth of the Telecommunication services.

The Government of India recognizes that provision of world-class telecommunication infrastructure and information is the key to rapid economic and social development of the country. It is critical not only for the development of the information Technology industry, But also has widespread ramifications on the entire economy of the country. The Indian Telecom sector is passing through a dynamic midway phase, as it is clearly undergoing the operation of market forces of demand and supply. The sovereignty of consumers is quite evident through their revealed preference in favor of economically rational decisions. Therefore, the task facing the managers in telecom sector is to focus on those activities that result in meeting or exceeding customer expectations. Moreover, the forces of liberalization and globalization of telecommunication market have pressurized the companies to maintain their market share by focusing on retaining their current customer. They are being increasingly confronted with the challenges to attract their subscribers by providing high quality of services. With the increase in the cost of acquisition of new customers, cellular mobile companies continually seek new ways to acquire retain and increase their subscriber base. Thus the ability to retain existing customer is increasingly crucial in this industry. This is possible only by providing quality of services to the customers. That is why this study has been taken and this study may provide the telecom manager useful guidelines to provide service quality to enhance their customer satisfaction level. The study uses a survey of UDAIPUR customers to investigate the service quality in telecom sector including below mentioned major players operating in Udaipur:

In this paper, we are trying to identify the service quality gaps (i.e. gaps between expectation and perception) with help of Parasuraman's SERVQUAL model. Customer satisfaction is the key success factors for this industry and service quality is one of the important dimensions for attaining the customer satisfaction.

In the year 1988 Parasuraman's et al developed a model to measure the expectation & perception towards any service, which is named as a SERVQUAL model. In the context of Telecom service the model is based on following five dimensions:-

- Reliability dimension is concerned with the telecom sectors' ability to perform the service accurately and dependably.
- Responsiveness dimension is related with the employees' willingness to help customers and provide prompt services.
- Assurance dimension includes Employees' knowledge, courtesy and their ability to inspire trust and confidence.

- Empathy dimension is related with Caring, individualized attention given to customers or the ease of access, approachability and effort taken to understand customers' requirements.
- Tangibles dimension is all about the appearance of the physical facilities and Service related at telecom.

One of the aims of this study involves the use of SERVQUAL instrument in order to ascertain any actual or perceived gaps between customer expectations and perceptions of the service offered. Another aim of this paper is to point out how management of service improvement can become more logical and integrated with respect to the prioritized service quality dimensions and their affections on increasing/decreasing service quality gaps. In the following pages, after a brief review of the literature, the model of service quality gaps and the SERVQUAL methodology is demonstrated. Then, after a discussion, major conclusions are derived based on the analysis.

LITERATURE REVIEW

A Dar, A Mir & Malik (2013) has done A study titled "A Study of Insurance Facilities available in Jammu and Kashmir". The basic objective of this paper is to design the strategic framework for enhancing the customer satisfaction for the insurance sector of the State of Jammu and Kashmir.

Nasser.M ,Selle h & Gelaidan (2012) has done study titled "Factors Affecting Customer Satisfaction of Mobile Services in Yemen". The aim of this study is to find out the customer's satisfaction with Yemeni Mobile service providers. This study examined the relationship between perceived quality, perceived value, customer expectation, and corporate image with customer satisfaction.. The study found that the relationship between perceived value, perceived quality and corporate image have a significant positive influence on customer satisfaction, whereas customer expectation has positive but without statistical significance.

Banerjee & sah (2012) has done a study titled “A Comparative Study of Customer’ Perceptions of Service Quality Dimensions between Public and Private Banks in India”. The authors have tried to identify the gap between customer expectations and perception of the actual service received. Overall from this study it can be concluded that customers’ expectations are more with the private banks and the level of satisfaction is also higher while they deal with the private banks. In order to satisfy the customer the public banks should focus on improving the service in terms of tangibility, reliability responsiveness and empathy.

Loke, Taiwo, Salim & Downe (2011) have done a study titled “Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction in a Telecommunication Service Provider”. In this study, they have found that customers from the GSM telecommunication firm experienced a difference between expectation and perception on the service received. Results of this study will encourage strategy development for superior service quality management particularly in the areas of assurance, empathy and responsiveness.

Joshi, Khurana & khurana (2010) has done a study titled “Service Quality in Telecom Sector – A Study of Telecom Service Providers of Chandigarh, Panchkula and Mohali”. In this study authors explored the key dimensions of service quality for mobile services in the telecom sector and tried to ascertain which aspect of service quality have significant impact on customer satisfaction and after analysis they suggested remedial measures to the companies.

Daniel& Berinyuy (2010) has done a study titled “Using the Servqual Model to assess Service Quality and Customer Satisfaction-An Empirical study of grocery stores in Umea”. In this study trying to find out if the SERVQAL modal is used to measure of service quality in grocery stores and empirically finding out how consumers perceive service quality in grocery stores by identifying what dimensions bring satisfaction. General implication to management of grocery stores is that they should focus on all dimensions of service quality and make efforts to improve them in order to have better performance that would lead to higher perceived service quality and customer satisfaction.

Tung (2010) has done a study titled “Customer satisfaction, perceived value and customer loyalty: the mobile services industry in China”. The research found that perceived expectations, perceived quality, perceived value, perceived usefulness and perceived ease of use have a major positive effect on customer satisfaction with mobile services. The research also concluded that customer satisfaction has a significantly positive direct impact on customer loyalty. Customer complaints have significantly negative direct impact on customer loyalty. Customer satisfaction has a significantly negative direct impact on customer complaints.

Ranaweera & Neely (2003) has done a study “Some moderating effects on the service quality-customer retention link”. This study was limited by the fact that it was based on cross sectional data. Further, some of the constructs in this study such as inertia and indifference are relatively under-researched and as such, future research could attempt to build more robust measures of these constructs. This study also looked only at linear relationships between the various constructs. While the linear relationship between inertia and retention was non-significant, plausible arguments could indeed be developed to hypothesis non-linear relationships. Therefore, future research could pursue such non-linear relationships to test whether they better explain customer repurchase intentions.

OBJECTIVES

The purposes of this research paper are as follow:-

1. To study the important factors in service quality dimensions applicable to Telecom sector.
2. To know the level of customer satisfaction with service quality dimensions.
3. To identify the significance of difference between customers’ expectations and perceptions in Telecom sector.
4. To suggest measures for improving the quality and efficiency in Telecom sector.

SCOPE OF STUDY

Identifying service quality is essential for telecom services which ultimately results in the customer satisfaction, so in this view scope of study is really wide & valuable. The level of dissatisfaction will lead to take corrective actions.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The primary purpose of this research is to identify the customers' expectation & perception towards telecom sector outlet and find out the level of customer satisfaction. Therefore descriptive research design is used to serve the purpose.

Area of the Study

The research is conducted at Udaipur among customers of telecom sector outlets i.e. Airtel , BSNL, Tata indicom , Spice, Reliance, Hutch, etc.

Research Approach

To collect Primary data structured questionnaire was designed which was divided under two heads i.e. demographics & service quality. In first part respondents were asked to reveal their personal characteristics i.e. gender, age, education, income, occupation, name of the service provider & duration with them. In second part respondents were asked to evaluate parameters of service quality on a 5 point scale, separately for their expectation & perception.

Sampling

Sample size of this study was 50 & Convenience sampling method was adopted for sampling.

Time Frame of Study

The study was conducted during the period August 2013 to September 2013.

Analytical Tools

For analysis and interpretation Arithmetic mean & z-test were applied.

ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATIONS

Table 1: Demographic Profile of Respondents

Particulars	Classification	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	32	64%
	Female	18	36%
Education	Undergraduate	8	16%
	Graduate	13	26%
	Post Graduate	29	58%
Age Group	Below 25	39	78%
	Above 25	11	22%
Monthly Income	Less than Rs. 10,000	23	46%
	Rs. 10,001-20,000	17	34%
	More than Rs. 20,000	10	20%
Occupation	Own business	2	4%
	Student	40	80%
	Private service	3	6%
	Government service	5	10%
Select your service provider	Airtel	20	40%
	BSNL	15	30%
	Tata indicom	8	16%
	Idea	6	12%
	Reliance	13	26%
	Vodaphone	15	30%
Average visit at Telecom	Weekly	12	24%

sector outlet	Fortnightly	2	4%
	Monthly	23	46%
	Half yearly	7	14%
	Yearly	6	12%
Duration of relationship with Service provider's	Less than 2 years	11	22%
	2 to less than 3 years	14	28%
	3 to less than 4 years	8	16%
	4 to less than 5 years	7	14%
	Above 5 years	10	20%

As per shown in table 1, demographics of respondents were classified according to their gender, education, age, monthly income , occupation, average visits, service provider, & relationship with service provider at the telecom sector outlets. Out of total respondents 64% are male & rests are female. Majority of respondents are post graduate (58%) & 78% respondents belong to the age group of below 25 years. 46% of respondents have their monthly income below Rs. 10,000 and Majority of respondents are students (80%). Majority of respondents (46%) visit the telecom sector outlets once in a month and 24% customers visit on a weekly basis.

From the above table it is clear that majority of the respondents have selected Airtel as their service provider followed by BSNL & Vodaphone. The above table shows that 28% of the respondents had maintained a relationship with the service provider for 2 to less than 3 years. These results indicate that there was relatively higher degree of instability of the customers. Customer in case of Telecom Company does not maintain a long time relationship with the provider and loyalty is highly dependent on service quality of these providers.

Customers’ Expectation & Perception towards Service Quality

This part included analysis on the basis of five factors according to service quality dimensions of the SERVQUAL system: tangibility, reliability, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy based on Parasuraman et al. (1988) Model. The researcher explored customer’s expectation and perception levels towards service quality of the restaurant chains and fast-food outlets.

The degree of satisfaction towards service quality is set from 1 to 3 (3 is from the high expectation/perception, whereas, 1 is the low expectation/perception).

In addition following criteria is used for analysis part:-

The score among 1.00-1.66 mean low satisfaction

The score among 1.67-2.33 mean average satisfaction

The score among 2.34-3 mean high satisfaction

Table: 2 Customers’ Expectation & Perception towards Reliability Dimension:

Reliability	Level of Expectation		Level of Perception		Mean Quality Gap Score
	Mean	Level	Mean	Level	
Telecom sector outlet provides you service as promised (like Network quality, Plans of internet, talktime, SMS etc.)	2.6	High	2.12	Medium	-.48
Telecom sector outlet perform the service at right time	2.42	High	2.12	Medium	-.30
Telecom sector provide service according to customer wants and needs	2.4	High	2.24	Medium	-.16

Telecom sector outlet services are error free	2.04	Medium	1.96	Medium	-.08
Overall Mean Score	2.365	High	2.11	Medium	-.255

Interpretation:

Table shows that for most of the parameters under “Reliability” dimension customers’ expectations are at high level and customers’ perceptions are at Medium level. Overall expectation of customers’ concerning “Reliability” dimension is high (2.365) & perception towards this dimension is at Medium level (2.11). All of the mean quality gap scores are negative which reveals the inefficiency of telecom sector outlets towards reliability dimension. The overall mean quality gap score is negative (-0.255) which shows that telecom sector outlets is not completely able to perform the promised services accurately.

Table: 3 Customers’ Expectation & Perception towards Responsiveness Dimension:

Responsiveness	Level of Expectation		Level of Perception		Mean Quality Gap Score
	Mean	Level	Mean	Level	
Telecom sector outlet tell exactly when services will be provided	2.46	High	2.3	Medium	-.16
Telecom sector outlet are willing to help you every time	2.32	Medium	2.04	Medium	-.28
Telecom sector outlet give you prompt service	2.52	High	2.82	High	.3
Telecom sector outlet are able to handle customer complaints directly	2.51	High	2.06	Medium	-.45

and immediately					
Overall Mean Score	2.452	High	2.305	Medium	-.147

Interpretation:

From the above table it is clear that for most of the parameters under “Responsiveness” dimension customers’ expectations are at high level whereas perceptions are at Medium level except in case of prompt service both the expectation and perception level is high. Overall expectation is high (2.452551) but perception of customers’ concerning “Responsiveness” dimension is Medium i.e. 2.305. Majority of mean quality gap scores are negative which reveals the inefficiency of telecom sector outlets towards responsiveness dimension but positive gap (.3) at prompt service parameter shows that telecom sector outlets performs the service within the expected time. Overall mean quality gap score is negative (-.147551) which shows that some improvements are required towards this dimension.

Table: 4 Customers’ Expectation & Perception towards Assurance Dimension

Assurance	Level of Expectation		Level of Perception		Mean Quality Gap Score
	Mean	Level	Mean	Level	
The behavior of employees in Telecom sector outlet instill confidence in customers	2.7	High	2.2	Medium	-.5
Employees of Telecom sector outlet are courteous with customers	2.42	High	2.22	Medium	-.2
Employees of Telecom sector outlet are well qualified and perform the	2.38	High	2.1	Medium	-.28

jobs accurately					
Employees of Telecom sector outlet are trustworthy	2.44	High	2.16	Medium	-.28
Employees of Telecom sector outlet has sufficient product knowledge	2.58	High	2.14	Medium	-.44
Overall Mean Score	2.504	High	2.164	Medium	-.34

Interpretation:

It can be seen from the above table that all parameters under “Assurance” dimension customers’ expectations are at high level and customer perception are at Medium level. Overall expectation is high 2.054 but perception of customers’ concerning this dimension is Medium 2.164 respectively. The overall mean quality gap score is negative (-.34) which shows that staff don’t have enough knowledge, trust & confidence among customers.

Table: 5 Customers’ Expectation & Perception towards Empathy Dimension

Empathy	Level of Expectation		Level of Perception		Mean Quality Gap Score
	Mean	Level	Mean	Level	
Telecom sector outlet has operating hours convenient to all their customers.	2.56	High	2.26	Medium	-.3
Employees of Telecom sector outlet give personal attention to customers	2.5	High	2.34	High	-.16
Employees of Telecom sector outlet understand needs of customers	2.46	High	2.34	High	-.12

Telecom sector outlet has variety in their services	2.56	High	2.3	Medium	-.21
Overall Mean Score	2.52	High	2.31	Medium	-.21

Interpretation:

Table shows that level of expectation & perception for all parameters concerning “Empathy” dimension customers’ expectations are at high level but customer perception are at Medium in case of convenient hrs. & service variety whereas it is high in case of personal attention & need recognition by employees. Overall expectation is high 2.52 but perception of customers’ concerning this dimension is Medium i.e. 2.31 respectively which has produced negative mean quality gap score (-0.21) & it shows deficiency in efforts taken by employees in understanding customers’ requirements.

Table: 6 Customers’ Expectation & Perception towards Tangibles Dimension

Tangibles	Level of Expectation		Level of Perception		Mean Quality Gap Score
	Mean	Level	Mean	Level	
Outlet of telecom companies are neat & clean	2.64	High	2.54	High	-.1
Location of telecom service outlet is convenient	2.42	High	2.34	High	-.08
Visually appealing physical facilities.	2.3	Medium	2.16	Medium	-.14
Professional appearance of employees.	2.46	High	2.38	High	-.08
Visually appealing materials.	2.46	High	2.18	Medium	-.28
Overall Mean Score	2.456	High	2.32	Medium	-.136

Interpretation:

It can be seen from the above table that on majority of the parameters under “Tangibles” dimension customers’ expectations are exactly equal to the customers’ perception except in case of visual appeal of the materials.. Overall expectation is high 2.456 & perception of customers’ is Medium 2.32, which has produced negative mean quality gap score (-0.136). But it is very minute gap so we can say that customers are satisfied with tangibles associated with telecom sector outlets & only little more inputs are required in order to nullify the gap.

HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Although that there is a negative difference between customer expectation & perception for all the parameters which leads to the customer dissatisfaction, still the significance of difference between mean scores should be identified.

So Let us take the hypothesis that

H₀: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of Expectation & Perception for any dimension.

H₁: There is a significant difference between the mean scores of Expectation & Perception for any dimension

Table 7

Attributes		Mean	S.D.	Z-value	P-value	Result
Reliability	Expectation	2.365	0.591017	1.923	0.0545	NS
	Perception	2.11	0.727847			
Responsiveness	Expectation	2.452	0.644478	0.997	0.3188	NS
	Perception	2.305	0.818891			
Assurance	Expectation	2.504	0.725777	1.583	0.1134	NS
	Perception	2.164	1.334049			

Empathy	Expectation	2.52	0.668135	1.449	0.1473	NS
	Perception	2.31	0.776338			
Tangibles	Expectation	2.456	0.682254	0.926	0.3544	NS
	Perception	2.32	0.782453			

Note: Level of significance is 5%, S- Significant, NS- Not Significant, Tabulated Value: 1.96

Table shows that all the calculated vales of z-test are less than tabulated value, which proves that there is no significant difference between the mean scores or the difference is negligible which can be removed by putting little efforts.

CONCLUSION

Service quality is an important aspect for telecom sector outlets to know about customers' satisfaction & SERVQUAL model is the root way to measure the effectiveness of service quality. In this paper, gap has been identified between expectation & perception of customers towards the telecom sector outlets of Udaipur, which revealed dissatisfaction among customers. However, Z-test results projected the insignificance of differences it means gaps can be easily removed by improving the level of service quality.

SUGGESTIONS

Telecom sector outlets of Udaipur can take following actions to reduce the mean quality gap score:-

- Employees of Telecom outlets should be trained to handle the customers' complaints effectively and should also be able to understand the unsaid needs of the customers.
- Proper attention should be given on the greviance handing department.
- Employees should have sufficient knowledge about all services offered by the outlet.

- Telecom outlets should try to give personalized services to customers.

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